

NEW COMPOSITE MATERIALS FOR RAILWAY APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The high mechanical properties to density ratio of composite materials make them very attractive for transportation industries, where an important key factor is the energy consumption and the capability of increase capacity. In this regard, the use of light materials as composites could decrease the weight obtaining energy savings and make possible the increase of payload.

The main problem to implement composite materials within the railway sector is that each component and assembly in the complete train needs to fulfil the Fire, Smoke and Toxicity (FST) requirements described in standard EN 45545. At present, there are few resins that comply with this regulation, due to the recent incorporation of this standard, which was approved in 2013. The resins, which comply with this standard, are highly doped increasing the viscosity. A high viscosity matrix is more difficult to process, making that the fabrication of the laminates becomes a challenge.

A preliminary selection of materials developed for railway industry was done in this work. Furthermore, an extensive characterisation was made to find the best material as possible for the different railway applications.

Using prepreg-based materials, a comparison between two different processes (autoclave and furnace) was carried out. The main aim is to get a preliminary evaluation and compare the different materials between each other.

1 INTRODUCTION

Continuous fibre reinforced polymer composites have been developed during the last decades to provide a wide range of materials, which combine high mechanical properties with light-weight [1,2]. FRP composites have been used for different applications [3-5] in aerospace, marine, civil infrastructures, etc. However, the use of composite materials has not been implemented yet in the railway industry for primary structures (e.g. carbody or running gears). The rigorous fire, smoke and toxicity requirements (FST) of this industry have been the main reason.

The resins, which meet the severe FST requirements according to the standard EN 45545 [6], usually have a high percentage of additives. High additive loading increases the viscosity, which affects the processing and the right impregnation of the fibres. Furthermore, the high viscosity of the matrix avoids the evacuation of the volatiles formed during the curing process and hinders the extraction of air bubbles. Therefore, to obtain a high-performance laminate with these resins is a big challenge to overcome during the next years.

A selection of available composite materials for railway industry was carried out within the European project Performance Improvement for Vehicles on Track project (PIVOT) and was showed in the present work.

In addition, an extensive characterization of the different materials was performed in order to find the best possible choice according to the different applications. Depending on the application, some of the following requirements are needed:

- Thermal properties
- Mechanical properties
- Fire resistance
- Noise attenuation

An advanced knowledge about the properties and processability of composite materials, which comply with FST requirements, could open an interesting chance for the railway industry. The development of these materials could enhance the vehicles on track performance and the current manufacturing processes.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Two different manufacturing processes were applied to consolidate the prepreg-based laminates: using an autoclave and out of autoclave, curing in a furnace. In addition, two different types of fibres were used: glass fibre and carbon fibre.

2.1. Materials

The main characteristics of the selected prepreg-based composites were summarized in the Table 1. Three different resins have been used as a matrix in the present work: epoxy, phenolic and polyfurfuryl alcohol (PFA).

- Epoxy (Epoxy1-Glass, Epoxy1-Carbon, Epoxy2-Carbon, Semipreg1-Carbon and Semipreg2-Carbon). Epoxy resins are widely used in high performance applications due to their mechanical performance per unit of mass. For the railway sector, these resins are highly doped to fulfil the FST requirements. Due to this high amount of FST filler, the viscosity used to be really high, being really hard to process and eliminate the volatiles by using conventional composite processes [7].
- Phenolic (Phenolic-Glass fibre and Phenolic-Carbon fibre materials). In general, phenolic resins cure by a condensation-reaction with the off-gassing of water. They are resins difficult to process but with excellent FST properties [7]. Regarding ancillary materials, phenolic resins cannot be in contact with polyamide, a polymer widely present in vacuum bagging films.
- Polyfurfuryl alcohol (PFA-Carbon fibre). It is a bio-resin system also referred to as furan resin [8]. In order to improve the processability of PFA, water can be added to these resins. This water added and the water /chemical products produced during the polycondensation reaction of the curing produces, affects the quality of the composite [8,9].

We have also used “semipreg” materials, which is a carbon fibre fabric partially impregnated with a resin film. In this case, high viscosity resins can be applied compared to a standard infusion resin system.

Table 1. Prepreg and semipreg-based materials selected for the characterization.

Name	Fibre	Matrix	EN45545	Resin weight (%)
Phenolic-Glass	Glass	Phenolic	HL3	35
Phenolic-Carbon	Carbon	Phenolic	HL3	48
Furan-Carbon	Carbon	Furan	HL3	40
Epoxy1-Glass	Glass	Epoxy ¹⁾	HL2	38
Epoxy1-Carbon	Carbon	Epoxy ¹⁾	HL2	48
Epoxy2-Carbon	Carbon	Epoxy	HL2	45
Semipreg1-Carbon	Carbon	Epoxy	HL2	48
Semipreg2-Carbon	Carbon	Epoxy	HL1	42

1) to autoclave processing

Only PFA and phenolic resins meet with HL3 requirements (Table 1), but their mechanical properties are lower than those of epoxy resins.

2.2 Manufacturing process

For all the materials, the manufacturing process will be divided in the following steps:

- a) Tooling preparation
- b) Ply cutting and Hand Lay-Up
- c) Vacuum bag
- d) Curing
- e) Post-curing (depending on the curing cycle provided by the manufacturer)
- f) Visual inspection
- g) C-Scan
- h) Optical Microscopy Analysis

In general, for all the manufactured panels the vacuum bag scheme will be the represented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Vacuum bagging scheme used for pre-impregnated composite materials.

Once the vacuum of the bag is checked, the curing cycle was applied following the recommendations of the manufacturer, summarized in Table 2. The curing cycle was carried out using the autoclave and the furnace.

Table 2. Manufacturing parameters used for each material.

Material	Process	Fabrication parameters		
		Temp (°C)	Time (min)	Pressure (bar)
Phenolic-Glass	Autoclave	135	75	4
	Furnace			-
Phenolic-Carbon	Autoclave	135	75	4
	Furnace			-
PFA-Carbon	Autoclave	130	60	6
	Furnace			-
Epoxy1-Glass	Autoclave	120	60	6.2
	Furnace			-
Epoxy1-Carbon	Autoclave	120	60	6.2
	Furnace			-
Epoxy2-Carbon	Autoclave	120	45	6
	Furnace			-
Semipreg1-Carbon	Autoclave	120	60	6
	Furnace			-
Semipreg2-Carbon	Autoclave	120	60	2.8
	Furnace			-

2.3. Optical microscopy

Optical microscopy images were taken from the thickness of each laminate in order to obtain a visual inspection of the laminate. Unimpregnated areas, voids and the distribution of the additives could be observed analysing the optical microscopy images. The surface analysed for each laminate was around 20x20 mm².

2.4. Mechanical testing

The mechanical properties of the laminates were determined through in-plane shear and interlaminar tests. In-plane shear (IPSS) tests were performed according to standard EN6031 [10]. The procedure is based on the uniaxial tensile stress-strain response of a $\pm 45^\circ$ laminate, which is symmetrically laminated about the mid-plane.

Short beam shear (SBS) test was carried out according to standard EN2563 [11]. The procedure of the test consists in to determine the resistance to delamination under shear forces parallel to the layers of the laminate. A rectangular cross section coupon is tested in flexure between two supports. The load was applied in the centre of the sample by means of a loading nose midway between the supports.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Morphology characterization

The thickness of the laminates was analysed by optical microscopy. An increase in porosity and voids was found in the laminates consolidated out of autoclave. As an example, a comparison between a laminate cured in autoclave and a laminate cured out of autoclave can be observed in Figure 2. In the laminate fabricated out of autoclave (Figure 2 b)) could be found a higher number of voids and defects than in the laminate manufactured in the autoclave (Figure 2 a)).

Figure 2. Optical microscopy image of a) laminate cured in autoclave, b) laminate cured out of autoclave.

On the other hand, some laminates made out of autoclave showed low porosity and defects percentage indicating that a good consolidation could be reached without autoclave (Figure 3). Furthermore, in Figure 3 additives were observed within the matrix. This addition increased the viscosity of the matrix making the processing more difficult.

In general, the epoxy-based laminates showed better morphological results than PFA and phenolic-based laminates, probably due to the complex crosslinking process of the PFA and phenolic resins.

Figure 3. Exemplary optical microscopy image of a laminate cured out of autoclave. Some additives were found within the matrix.

3.2. Mechanical properties

In-plane shear and short beam shear test were carried out to characterize the mechanical properties of the laminates. As it was expected, the laminates cured in autoclave showed better mechanical properties than the laminates fabricated by using a furnace, probably due to the highest quality of the autoclave samples (low porosity).

4. CONCLUSIONS

A selection of composite materials was carried out in order to get the best composite materials, which can be applied in railway sector. This work was developed within the Performance Improvement for Vehicles On Track (PIVOT) project.

The recent incorporation of EN45545 limited the use of the traditional composite materials due to the FST requirements. For this reason, the materials made with this purpose are still being developed. To enhance the properties and the processability of these materials are the main aims.

The use of autoclave showed the best results. However, the use of this processing limits the application of these materials due to the high cost. On the other hand, some laminates fabricated out-of-autoclave showed low porosity. However, it is still necessary to improve these materials and their fabrication route.

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